

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF TRENDS IN EMERGING RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF TRENDS IN EMERGING RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

Volume 3; Issue 6; 2025; Page No. 60-64

Received: 18-08-2025

Accepted: 26-09-2025

Published: 17-11-2025

A study of attitude of secondary school teachers towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation of secondary education

¹Tuhina Khatun and ²Dr. Hazarat Ali Seikh

¹Student M.ED., University of Kalyani, Kalyani, West Bengal, India

²Associate Professor, Lalgola College, West Bengal, India

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17960919>

Corresponding Author: Tuhina Khatun

Abstract

Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation is very effective new scheme of evaluation. CCE is evaluate every aspect of child during their presence at the school it will reduce pressure on the child during /before examination and to improve the overall skill and ability of the student by means of evaluation of other activity. These efforts would not turn to be effective and successful if our teachers are not willing whole heartedly to implement such evaluation system in right manner and spirit. the main objective in this study the attitude of PG with B.Ed. and U.G with B. Ed teachers towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation. And to access the level of teacher's attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation. all the secondary school teachers under Lalgola and Bhagwan Gola police stations of Murshidabad district as population. Findings of the study is there no significant differences between the attitude of male and female teachers towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation and There are no significant differences between the attitude of teachers towards child related aspect of CCE.

Keywords: Continuous And Comprehensive Evaluation, Secondary School Teachers, Attitude

Introduction

In our country education has changed from gurukuls to present day schools with lot of facilities, in this process of change every aspect of education has changed and in the same way the process of evaluation also changed a lot. These days there is a lot of debate that Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation (CCE) pattern has adopted from west, but Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation (CCE) is not new to India. This has been there from time immemorial say Ramayana, Mahabharata periods which included all aspect of personality development of a student. Implementation of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation was one of the recommendations of Kothari Commission (1964-66). The recommendation was accepted by the govt. of India under National policy of Education (NPE), 1968 which was formulated on the basis of the recommendations of the Kothari commission. Since then, lot of changes was made by introducing unit test in place of

Term end exam of yearend exam. All the documents such as National Curriculum Framework (2000) and the National Curriculum framework (2005) also stressed on the implementation of the CCE. One of the important features of right to education act (RTE) was the introduction of continuous and comprehensive evaluation. Thus, CCE is implemented now during the tenure of shri Kapil Sibbal, minister of Human Resource Development. This is the new evaluation method introduced recently to decrease the accumulated stress of board exams.

To achieve the objectives of evaluation or to work on the functions of evaluation "The central Board of Secondary Education introduced Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation (CCE) in Primary classes in 2004. The achievement records and its formats was also circulated for classes I to V with the objective of recommendation a five-point rating scale, it also recommended the elimination of the pass/fail system at the primary classes. The Board has

also followed it up by extending this scheme up to classes VI to VIII and developed a CCE cardon School Based Assessment for the same Circular.

The scheme of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation (CCE) will be now further strengthened in all affiliated schools from October 2009. The Class IX students will be assessed through the CCE by the school itself.

Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation refers to a system of school-based assessment that covers all aspects of student's development. The comprehensive component of CCE takes care of assessment of all round development of the child personality. As a part of this new system, student grades are given instead of marks which will be evaluated through a series of curricular and Extra-curricular evaluations along with academics. The aim is to reduce the workload on students and to improve other skills; more emphasis is given on expression or presentation ability of the student with the help of so many activities inside and outside the school. Grades and awarded to students based on work experience skills, innovation, steadiness, teamwork, public speaking, behaviour, etc. to evaluate and present an overall measure of the student's ability. This type of evaluation helps the student who are not good at studies they get the chance to perform in other field like art, games, robotics, athletics etc. CBSE's old pattern of only one test at the end of the academic year, the CCE conducted several. There are two different types of tests the formative and the summative. Through Formative tests student's work at class and home, the student's performance in oral tests and quizzes and the quality of the projects or assignment submitted by the child are judge. Formative tests will be conducted four times in an academic session, and they will carry a 40% weightage for the aggregate.

Rationale of the study

The outcome of this system of CCE at the initial level varies. Through most of the school implemented it quickly, teachers were more connected to the older system and examination faced difficulties coping with the changes. This study can help to change the attitude of teachers towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation. The workload is now here reduced in truth, because even through the exams have been cut off, students wrestle with time and effort making projects and preparing for oral tests all the year round. Even if the syllabus is not covered, one needs to participate in activities. But the outcomes by this method were projected to be better than rote learning of the previous system which placed an undue emphasis on memory and facts instead will appreciate it and some strongly depreciate it. If a child gets into the good book of a teacher, then he is able to get good grades throughout the year. Flattery is often used by some children to get into good books of a teacher.

Statement of the problem

Attitude towards Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation of Secondary School Teachers.

Review of Related Literature

Jaiswal, S. (2010)^[4] conducted a study of "teachers' attitude towards new evaluation system". The findings of the study were that there was a significant difference in the attitude of regular and para teachers. Some teachers have negative

attitude towards this system due to unsuccessful implementation of this system. The findings revealed that Para teachers had less positive attitude towards this system than regular teachers. The para teachers were untrained for this system. To make the teachers attitude towards this system, it is needed that a proper training should be organised to all the teachers, so that they can understand its various aspects. It had also been found that there was a significant difference between male and female teachers with respect to their attitude towards this system. Observation of their mean values revealed that male teachers had more positive attitude than female teachers. The reason behind this was that the execution of this system needed to have mathematical skill, which is generally lacking in female teachers. So, to ensure the active participation of female teachers, it is needed that the procedure should be made somewhat easy to deal with.

Singhal, P. (2012)^[14] conducted a study on "Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation: A study of teachers perception". The study followed the design of a descriptive survey and consisted a sample of 100 government school teachers from Delhi region. The result of the study is that currently the perception of government school teachers is average which indicates moderate acceptability of CCE by the teachers and large number of students in the classes, lack of appropriate training, inadequate infrastructure and teaching materials and increased volume of work act as barriers in smooth execution of CCE.

Singh Avtar, *et al.* (2013)^[13] conducted research on "attitude of student teacher towards Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation with reference to Gender, Caste and Habitat". The population of the study constituted all student in the B.Ed. programme. The population i.e.180 students of B.Ed. course, being too small, the entire population was taken for the sample. A five-point Likert scale was used. It was found that the Attitude of B.Ed. students towards continuous internal assessment was moderately favourable. There was no significant difference in the mean attitude towards continuous internal assessment of male and female B.Ed. students; students belonging to different habitat and student belonging to different caste categories.

Kumar & Kumar (2014)^[5] explored the secondary school teacher's awareness about the scheme of CCE and the problems they face while its execution. After interviewing 30 secondary school teachers, the findings revealed that majority of the teachers possessed awareness towards the policy. The study also took account of the problems that teachers face during the execution of the CCE. Overcrowding in the classroom, lack of proper training of teachers regarding the CCE, lack of adequate infrastructure and teaching materials, increased volume of work, cost factor, time consumed and lack or parents interest towards CCE are the major factors that hinder the effective implementation of CCE.

Rathee, I. (2014)^[9] conducted a study on "Teachers Attitude about the system of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation". It consists 100 teachers as sample from government and non-government schools. For data collection, the investigator used, 'Teacher Attitude scale towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation' developed by Dr. Vishal Sood and Dr. Arti Anand. The

result of the study revealed that most of the teachers have highly favourable attitude towards CCE. In addition, teachers have some kind of attitude towards CCE in relation to their subject and teaching experience.

Acharya & Mondal (2015) ^[1] conducted research study on “Teacher’s awareness school on continuous and comprehensive evaluation at Elementary schools”. The main objectives of the study were to find out the knowledge of teachers on continuous and comprehensive evaluation at Elementary schools of Lakhimpur District of Assam in relation to professional qualification, settlement and gender. Questionnaire was used to collect the data. The major findings of the study, there is no significant difference between the Trained and Untrained Elementary school teachers on the knowledge of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation (CCE) in Lakhimpur district of Assam.

Raina & Verma (2015) ^[8] conducted A study on “Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation-A study of Teacher Attitude”. Data was collected from teachers (N = 144) of CBSE affiliated schools of Jammu province. Statistical tools like Analysis of variance and t test were used to study the significance difference between the various group. The overall result indicates that there is a significant difference between attitude of teachers towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation in relation to the interaction of school type, qualification and locality.

Singh, B. (2017) ^[12] conducted A study of “Attitude Towards Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation”. The aim of the study the attitude of senior secondary school students towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation (CCE) on their study habit in Allahabad. A sample of 200 students of senior secondary school of CBSE board of Allahabad has been taken for the study through simple random technique. study showed that there is a significant positive correlation between attitude of senior secondary school students towards CCE and their study habits and students had fairly favourable study habits exhibited fairly favourable attitude towards CCE. Further there is a significant difference between most favourable and least favourable group of attitudes towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation of students on their study habits and Attitude of male and female students do not differ significantly towards CCE.

Hassan, M. (2016) ^[3] conducted a study of “Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation in Secondary School”. This study Was designed to assess the awareness and explore the problems of students regarding Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation. The sample of the study consist of 120 students drawn from four CBSE affiliated secondary schools located at Bilaspur and Raipur districts of Chhattisgarh through purposive sampling technique. A self-constructed inventory having 47 items was used for data collection. Semi structured interview was also conducted to explore students’ problems regarding CCE. The findings of the study will draw the attention of all the stakeholders, especially policy planners and school administration to take necessary steps for smooth functioning of CCE in secondary schools.

Shah, A. (2017) ^[10] Conducted A Study on “School Teacher Attitude Towards Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation”. The main objective of this research was to

study the level of school teachers’ attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation and to compare the male and female school teachers as well as urban and rural school teachers’ attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation. The findings of the study indicate that there was no significant difference between the male and female school teachers’ attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation and there was no significant difference between school teachers’ attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation working in urban and rural areas.

Srilatha & Reddy (2017) ^[15] The present study is an attempt to assess the influence of gender and the experience of teachers on the attitude of school teacher towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation. The sample comprised of 150 teachers; of which 83 were male and 67 were female teachers. Attitude scale was developed to measure the teacher attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation. The study indicates that the general attitude level of the teachers towards CCE is at low level. Further the study revealed that the experience had influenced the attitude of the teacher towards continuous evaluation.

Sing, A. (2017) ^[12] Conducted A Study of “School Teachers Attitude Towards Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation”. The main objectives of this research were:(i) To study the level of school teachers’ attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation. (ii) To compare the male and female school teachers’ attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation and (iii) To compare the school teachers’ attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation working in urban and rural areas. The findings of the study were also indicated that there was no significant difference between the male and female school teachers’ attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation and there were no significant differences between school teachers’ attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation working in urban and rural areas.

Naidu, B. (2017) ^[7] studied was an analysis of “attitude of high schoolteachers towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation”. The data was collected from 100 high school teachers of east Godavari district of Andhra Pradesh through administration of a self -development tool. ‘t’ test was applied to study the significance of difference between various groups. The findings reveals that male and female, government and private, married and unmarried, rural and urban high school teachers do not differ on their attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation.

Manna, M. (2019) ^[6] Teachers Attitude towards Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation. A comparison of government and private Schools of Delhi. The success of any innovation in the field of education depends greatly upon its proper implementation by the practitioners. The implementation depends upon practitioners’ attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation as per CBSE scheme. Teachers should have sound attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation. Its lays emphasis on thought process and de-emphasizes memorization. CCE use a variety of ways to collect information about the learner’s learning and progress in different subject and co-curricular activities. For studying the school teachers’

attitude towards CCE. The study has been conducted on 200 school teachers in all, equal number from each of the school (10 teachers from 10 government and 10 private schools) The sample of 200 school teachers has been selected through random sampling method. A self-made attitude scale based on 5-point Likert's scale for assessing the school teachers' attitude towards CCE has been used by researcher. In Attitude scale, 40 items have been responded by 100 government and 100 Private school teachers.

Perception of Teachers on Implementation of CCE in the Upper Primary Schools of Delhi - NCR. This study attempts to find out perception of teachers towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation. Sample of 100 school teachers were randomly selected from Delhi and Faridabad. Self-made Questionnaire consists of 10 items for teachers was prepared and distributed among them. The findings revealed that the perception of upper primary school teachers of Delhi is better than that of NCR towards CCE.

Objectives

- To study the attitude of male and female teachers towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation.
- To study the teacher's attitude towards -
 - Teachers related aspect of CCE
 - Child related aspect of CCE
 - Process related aspect of CCE
- To study the attitude of PG with B.Ed. and U. G with B. Ed teachers towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation.
- To access the level of teacher's attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation.

Hypothesis of the study

- There is no significant differences between the attitude of male and female teachers towards CCE.
- There is no significant difference between the attitude of teachers related aspect of CCE, Child related aspect of CCE and Process related aspect of CCE.
- There is no significant difference between the attitude of P.G with B.Ed. and U.G with B.Ed. teachers towards CCE.

Operational definition

Attitude: Attitude is personal and related of the feeling of a person as he thinks or behaves.

Secondary school Teacher: Secondary school teachers mean the teacher possessing basic qualification of B. ED and teaching secondary classes in secondary school.

Continuous and comprehensive evaluation: Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation means a system of evaluation that proceeds throughout the academic session and covers all the aspects of student's development.

Technique employed for development of attitude scale

The method of summated ratings as given by Likert (1932) [16] has been employed for development of present attitude scale. Each item/statement of the scale is rated on five consecutive points i.e. strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree, strongly disagree. The individual teachers score on the attitude scale is the sum total of his/her ratings on all

statements/items.

After conducting item analysis and selecting the statement for final draft, the distribution of statements (both positive and negative) was carried out in three aspect/dimensions of teacher's attitude towards CCE.

Table 1: Distribution of statement (both positive and negative) was carried out in three aspects/dimensions of teacher's attitude towards CCE

Sl. No.	Aspect	Positive Item	Negative Item	Total
1	Child related	14	8	22
2	Teacher related	7	6	13
3	Process related	6	7	13
	Total	27	21	48

Table 2: Scoring procedure of TASTCCE- SA Scale

Number of items	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Positive	5	4	3	2	1
Negative	1	2	3	4	5

Table 3: Correlation coefficients showing internal consistency of Tastece (N=120)

Serial Number	Aspect	'r' value
1	Child - related	0.79**
2	Teacher - related	0.73**
3	Process - related	0.69**

**significance at 0.01 level of significance

Major Findings of the study

- There is no significant differences between the attitude of male and female teachers towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation
- There is no significant differences between the attitude of teachers towards child related aspect of CCE.
- There is no significant differences between the attitude of teachers towards process related aspect of CCE
- There is no significant differences between the attitude of PG with B. ED and UG with B. ED teachers towards CCE

Educational Implication

- Teachers should not be discriminated on the basis of being male and female for the effect of work load on their teaching effectiveness
- Teachers should not be discriminated on the basis of being educational qualification
- Working condition for the teachers should improve
- Collaborative relationships with Teachers and students
- Salaries and other benefit should provide to all teachers without discrimination.

Conclusion

The role of continuous and comprehensive evaluation is very important where our aim is to improve learners to quality in the cognitive as well as non-cognitive domains. In the context of school, it is a continuous updating of teachers about their students. CCE facilities students effective learning as well as their all-round development of personality with its multiple tools, technique and corrective measures. It is an integral part of learning process which promotes standard of school.

Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation is very effective new scheme of evaluation. CCE is evaluate every aspect of child during their presence at the school it will reduce pressure on the child during /before examination and to improve the overall skill and ability of the student by means of evaluation of other activity. These efforts would not turn to be effective and successful if our teachers are not willing whole heartedly to implement such evaluation system in right manner and spirit.

References

1. Acharya P, Mondal M. Teachers' awareness on Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation at elementary schools of Assam. Shrinkhla: Ek Shodhparak Vaicharik Patrika. 2015. p. 22–26.
2. Chopra V, Bhatia R. Practice of teachers in implementing continuous and comprehensive evaluation: an exploratory study. MIER Journal of Educational Studies, Trends and Practices. 2014;4(1):16–32.
3. Emimah S. Attitude of secondary school mathematics teachers towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation. Imperial Journal of Interdisciplinary Research. 2016;2(3):554–567.
4. Jaiswal S. A study of teachers' attitude towards the new evaluation system. International Research Journal of Research Analysis and Evaluation. 2010;1(3–4):78.
5. Kumar A, Kumar R. A study on awareness of continuous and comprehensive evaluation among secondary school teachers. Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies. 2014;3(17):3114–3119.
6. Manna M. Teachers' attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation: a comparison of government and private schools of Delhi. Maharaja Surajmal Institute Journal of Applied Research. 2019;2(1):1–8.
7. Naidu MB. An analysis of attitude of high school teachers towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation. International Journal of Academic Research. 2017;4(1):121–131.
8. Raina S, Verma LK. Continuous and comprehensive evaluation: a study of teachers' attitude. International Journal of Recent Scientific Research. 2015;6(9):6180–6183.
9. Rathee I. A study of teachers' attitude. Review of Research. 2014;3(12):1–5.
10. Shah A. A study of school teachers' attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation. Bhartiya International Journal of Education and Research. 2017;6(3):14–20.
11. Sharma K. Attitude of teachers towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation. Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies. 2015;3(18):193–200.
12. Singh A. A study of school teachers' attitude towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation. Bhartiya International Journal of Education and Research. 2017;6(3). ISSN: 2277-1255.
13. Singh A, *et al.* Attitude of student teachers towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation with reference to gender, caste and habitat. [Journal Name Not Specified]. 2013;2(1):65–80.
14. Singhal P. Continuous and comprehensive evaluation: a study of teachers' perception. Delhi Business Review. 2012;13(1):81–99.
15. Srilatha B, Reddy K. A study on the attitude of teachers towards continuous and comprehensive evaluation. International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. 2017;7(11):38–43.
16. Likert R. Escala de Likert. Recuperado el. 1932;11.

Creative Commons (CC) License

This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0) license. This license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.